

**Beyond Science and Decisions:
From Problem Formulation to Dose-Response
Report from Workshop VIII - Appendices**

Workshop Held:
May 21, 22, 2014
Austin, Texas
at the Texas Commission on Environmental Quality

Appendices

August 18, 2014

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Appendix 1. Biographies for Standing Panel Members

Science Panel

Richard Beauchamp, Texas Department of State Health Services

Richard A. Beauchamp is the Senior Medical Toxicologist for the Texas Department of State Health Services (DSHS) with responsibility for providing advanced toxicological and risk assessment support for the Exposure Assessment, Surveillance, and Toxicology (EAST) Group. As cooperative agreement partners with the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR), Dr. Beauchamp and other EAST Group members are tasked with conducting Public Health Assessments at abandoned hazardous waste sites that are proposed and added to the Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA's) National Priority List (NPL) of Superfund sites in Texas. Dr. Beauchamp is also involved with conducting other medical and toxicological Public Health Consultations involving exposures to environmental hazardous substances.

After earning his medical degree at the University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio (1973-1977), Dr. Beauchamp completed a three year pediatric residency with the Austin Pediatric Education Program at Brackenridge Hospital in Austin, Texas (1977-1980) and began working at the Texas Department of Health as a Public Health Physician Epidemiologist (1980). Early in his career at the health department, he was tasked with developing risk assessment expertise that would be essential for the newly-formed Environmental Epidemiology Program in the evaluation of environmental and chemical exposures. With an undergraduate degree in Electrical Engineering (U.T. Austin) and a strong background in mathematics and computer sciences, Dr. Beauchamp has applied the knowledge gained through participation at numerous risk assessment conferences, symposia, and seminars (sponsored by EPA, NGA, CDC, ASTHO, NIOSH, and others) to the development of his so-called "Risk Assessment Toolkit." Dr. Beauchamp's toolkit consists of a series of Excel® spreadsheets designed for the flexible and rapid evaluation of cancer and non-cancer risks resulting from exposures to a wide variety of environmental contaminants through all of the common exposure pathways. Risks are calculated incrementally using age-specific exposure parameters, including body weights, body surface areas, respiratory daily volumes, and EPA's early-life exposure factors. Risks are integrated over the exposure duration, using up to 46 different age intervals, to insure that childhood exposures are appropriately addressed.

James S. Bus, Exponent

James S. Bus is a Senior Managing Scientist in the Center for Toxicology and Mechanistic Biology in the Health Sciences Group of Exponent, a leading global consulting firm (May 2013-present). His primary responsibilities at Exponent are to provide toxicology expertise for addressing client product stewardship and regulatory needs associated with industrial and pesticide chemicals. Prior to joining Exponent, Dr. Bus retired from The Dow Chemical Company as Director of External Technology, Toxicology and Environmental Research and Consulting (1989-2013). He also previously held positions as Associate Director of Toxicology and Director of Drug Metabolism at The Upjohn Company (1986-1989), Senior Scientist at the Chemical Industry Institute of Toxicology (CIIT, 1977-1986), and Assistant Professor of Toxicology, University of Cincinnati (1975-1977). Dr. Bus currently serves on the Boards of Directors of The Hamner Institutes (formerly CIIT) and the ILSI Research Foundation. He has also served as Chair of the American Chemistry Council and International Council of Chemical Associations Long-Range Research Initiatives; the Board of Directors of ILSI-HESI; the USEPA Office of Research and Development Board of Scientific Counselors (1997-2003) and Chartered Science Advisory Board (2003-2009); the National Toxicology Program Board of Scientific Counselors (1997-2000); the FDA National Center for Toxicological Research Science Advisory Board (2004-2010); and the National Academy of Sciences/National Research Council Board on Environmental Studies and Toxicology (BEST; 2005-2011). He has served as an Associate Editor of *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, and on the Editorial Boards of *Environmental Health Perspectives* and *Dose Response*. Dr. Bus is a member of the Society of Toxicology (serving as President in 1996-97), the American Society for Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics, the American Conference of Governmental and Industrial Hygienists, and the Teratology Society. He is a Diplomate and Past-President of the American Board of Toxicology and a Fellow of the Academy of Toxicological Sciences (member of Board of Directors, 2008-present; President, 2010-2011). Dr. Bus received the Society of Toxicology Achievement Award (1987) for outstanding contributions to the science of toxicology; the Society of Toxicology Founders Award (2010) for leadership fostering the role of toxicology in improving safety decisions; Rutgers University Robert A. Scala Award (1999) for exceptional work as a toxicologist in an industry laboratory; and the K.E. Moore Outstanding Alumnus Award (Michigan State University, Dept. Pharmacol. And Toxicol.). He received his B.S. in Medicinal Chemistry from the University of Michigan (1971) and Ph.D in pharmacology from Michigan State University (1975) and currently is an Adjunct Professor in the Dept. Pharmacology and Toxicology at that institution. His research interests include mechanisms of oxidant toxicity, chemical and pesticide modes of action, defense mechanisms to chemical toxicity, relationships of pharmacokinetic and exposures information to expression of chemical toxicity, and general pesticide and industrial chemical toxicology. He has authored/co-authored over 100 publications, books, and scientific reviews.

Mike Dourson, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment

Mike Dourson is the President of Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment (TERA), a nonprofit corporation dedicated to the best use of toxicity data in risk assessment. Before founding TERA in 1995, Dr. Dourson held leadership roles in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency as chair of US EPA's Reference Dose (RfD) Work Group, charter member of the US EPA's Risk Assessment Forum and chief of the group that helped create the Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS). Dr. Dourson received his Ph.D. in Toxicology from the University of Cincinnati. He is a Diplomat of the American Board of Toxicology and a Fellow of the Academy of Toxicological Sciences. Dr. Dourson has served on or chaired numerous expert panels, including peer review panels for US EPA IRIS assessments, US EPA's Risk Assessment Forum, TERA's International Toxicity Estimates for Risk (*ITER*) independent peer reviews and consultations, FDA's Science Board Subcommittee on Toxicology, the NSF International's Health Advisory Board, and SOT's harmonization of cancer and non-cancer risk assessment. He served as Secretary for the Society for Risk Analysis (SRA) and has held leadership roles in specialty sections of SRA and SOT. He is currently on the editorial board of three journals. Dr. Dourson has published more than 100 papers on risk assessment methods, has co-authored over 100 government risk assessment documents, and has made over 100 invited presentations.

Annie M. Jarabek, U.S. EPA, Office of Research and Development

Annie M. Jarabek is a senior toxicologist in the immediate office of the National Center for Risk Assessment (NCEA) within the US EPA's Office of Research and Development (ORD). Annie is the principal author of the US EPA's Methods for Derivation of Inhalation Reference Concentrations (RfC) and Application of Inhalation Dosimetry, which introduced dosimetry and physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model structures and reduced forms into the RfC methods for interspecies adjustment. She has worked on several high-priority and interdisciplinary Agency assessments including the risk characterization of perchlorate ingestion and the inhalation of particulate matter (PM); and has served in an advisory capacity on other methods and assessments, including the guidance on body-weight scaling for harmonizing noncancer and cancer approaches for the interspecies adjustment of ingested chemicals. Her current research efforts focus on multi-scale modeling of dose-response and decision analysis. Annie has twice received awards for best manuscript in risk assessment application from the Risk Assessment Specialty Section (RASS) of the Society of Toxicology (SOT), along with several best abstract awards. She has also received the Lifetime Achievement Award from the University of Massachusetts, the Risk Practitioner of the Year award from the Society of Risk

Analysis (SRA), the Superfund National Notable Achievement Award, and several award medals (1 gold, 1 silver and 5 bronze) and “S awards” for scientific leadership from the Agency for her various contributions. Annie has served as an elected Councilor to the Society for Risk Analysis and as the vice-president/president of the SOT RASS. Annie has also served the SOT on its awards, communications, nominations, and scientific program committees. She is currently on the editorial board of the international journal “Dose-Response.”

R. Jeffrey Lewis, ExxonMobil Biomedical Sciences, Inc.

Dr. R. Jeffrey Lewis is currently Section Head of the Epidemiology, Health Surveillance and Quality Assurance group at ExxonMobil Biomedical Sciences, Inc (EMBSI). In this position, Dr Lewis is responsible for managing EMBSI’s Epidemiology and Health Surveillance group, the company’s laboratory quality assurance program, and for providing support to ExxonMobil scientific programs related to 1,3-butadiene, naphthalene, asphalt, legislative/regulatory affairs and regulatory impact analysis (e.g., benefit-cost analysis). He has served on a number of industry trade association scientific committees (e.g., the American Chemistry Council’s 1,3-butadiene Work Group), external science advisory boards (e.g., the Alliance for Risk Assessment Expert Science Panel) and is a member of the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) Threshold Limit Value (TLV) Committee. Dr. Lewis also has an adjunct faculty appointment at the University of Texas School of Public Health and is Past Treasurer for the Society for Risk Analysis. Dr. Lewis received his Bachelor of Science degree in biology from the University of Kansas in 1985 and a M.S. and Ph.D. in Epidemiology from the University of Texas School of Public Health in 1987 and 1990, respectively. In addition, he earned a Master of Business Administration degree from Rutgers University in 1997.

Bette Meek, McLaughlin Centre for Population Health Risk Assessment, University of Ottawa

Bette Meek has a background in toxicology receiving her M.Sc. in Toxicology (with distinction) from the University of Surrey, U.K. and her Ph.D. in risk assessment from the University of Utrecht, the Netherlands. She is currently the Associate Director of Chemical Risk Assessment at the McLaughlin Centre for Population Health Risk Assessment, University of Ottawa, completing an interchange assignment from Health Canada. She has extensive experience in the management of chemical assessment programs within the Government of Canada, most recently involving development and implementation of process and methodology for the health

assessment of Existing Substances under the Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA) and previously, programs for contaminants in drinking water and air.

With colleagues within Canada and internationally, she has contributed to or led initiatives to increase transparency, defensibility and efficiency in health risk assessment, having convened and participated in initiatives in this area for numerous organizations including the International Programme on Chemical Safety, the World Health Organization, the International Life Sciences Institute, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, the U.S. National Academy of Sciences and the U.S. National Institute for Environmental Health Sciences. Relevant areas have included frameworks for weight of evidence analysis including mode of action, chemical specific adjustment factors, physiologically-based pharmacokinetic modeling, combined exposures and predictive modeling. She has also authored over 175 publications in the area of chemical risk assessment and received several awards for contribution in this domain.

Moiz Mumtaz, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ad hoc)

Dr. Moiz Mumtaz, MSc, MS, PhD, FATS, is Science Advisor, Division of Toxicology and Human Health Sciences, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR), Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and an Associate Professor (adjunct), Emory University, Department of Environmental Health, Atlanta, Georgia, USA. He obtained his Ph.D. in toxicology from the University of Maryland and received his M.S. in chemistry/entomology from Oregon State University. Dr. Mumtaz started his professional career as a chemist after completing his M.Sc. in analytical chemistry from Osmania University, India.

Dr. Mumtaz is the ATSDR's principal representative on the Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) Interagency Coordinating committee on the validation of alternative methods (ICCVAM), and member of the Society of Toxicology (SOT) Toxic Substances Control Act subcommittee, SOT Government Liaison Group, and Oregon State University Superfund Center External Advisory Committee. He has served on several national and international workgroups/committees including the CDC's Cigarette Ingredients Toxicology Analysis Working Group, U.S. EPA Board of Scientific Counselors (BOSC) Computational Toxicology Subcommittee, EPA Guidelines Work Group for the Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures, the NIOSH Mixed Exposures Work Group, National Occupational Research Agenda, Research Working Group of Military and Veterans Health Coordinating Board, the Health Impact of Chemical Exposures during the Gulf War, Research Working Group of the Persian Gulf War Coordinating Board, Health Assessment Work Group of the Interagency Air

Assessment Team on Kuwaiti Crude Oil Fires. Dr. Mumtaz is a member of the Society of Toxicology, and the past- president of the SOT Mixtures Specialty Section.

In 2013, he was elected a Fellow of the Academy of Toxicological Sciences (FATS) and won the Society of Toxicology (SOT) Lehman award for major contributions to risk assessment and the regulation of chemical agents. During the past three decades, Dr. Mumtaz has actively published his research findings in several peer-reviewed journals. These publications have covered a wide range of research areas pertinent to medicine and human health including dopamine metabolism and mental health; comparative toxicology; chemical analysis of xenobiotics and environmental chemicals; health risk assessment of chemical mixtures and environmental stressors.

Greg Paoli, Risk Sciences International

Greg Paoli serves as Principal Risk Scientist and COO at Risk Sciences International, a consulting firm specializing in risk assessment, management and communication in the field of public health, safety and risk-based decision-support. Mr. Paoli has experience in diverse risk domains including toxicological, microbiological, and nutritional hazards, air and water quality, climate change impacts, medical and engineering devices, as well as emergency planning and response for natural and man-made disasters. He specializes in probabilistic risk assessment methods, the development of risk-based decision-support tools and comparative risk assessment. Mr. Paoli has served on a number of expert committees devoted to the risk sciences. He was a member of the U.S. National Research Council committee that issued the 2009 report, *Science and Decisions: Advancing Risk Assessment*. He serves on the Canadian Standards Association Technical Committee on Risk Management, advisory committees of the National Roundtable on the Environment and the Economy, a US NRC Standing Committee on the Use of Public Health Data at the U.S. Food Safety and Inspection Service, and has served on several expert committees convened by the World Health Organization. Mr. Paoli completed a term as Councilor of the Society for Risk Analysis (SRA) and is a member of the Editorial Board of *Risk Analysis*. Recently, Mr. Paoli was awarded the Sigma Xi – SRA Distinguished Lecturer Award. He has provided training in risk assessment methods around the world, including the continuing education programs of the Harvard School of Public Health and the University of Maryland. Greg holds a Bachelors Degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering and a Master's Degree in Systems Design Engineering from the University of Waterloo.

Alan Stern, New Jersey Department of Environmental Protection

Dr. Alan H. Stern is the Section Chief for Risk Assessment in the Office of Science of the New Jersey Department of Environmental Protection; Adjunct Associate Professor in the Department of Environmental and Occupational Health of the University of Medicine and Dentistry of New Jersey-School of Public Health. He received a bachelor's degree in biology from the State University of New York at Stony Brook (1975), a master's degree in cellular and molecular biology from Brandeis University (1978), a master of public health degree (1981) and a doctorate in public health from the Columbia University School of Public Health (1987). Dr. Stern is board-certified in toxicology by the American Board of Toxicology (Diplomate of the American Board of Toxicology). Dr. Stern's areas of expertise include risk assessment and exposure assessment including the application of probabilistic techniques to quantitative estimation of exposure and risk. His research interests have focused on heavy metals including lead, mercury, chromium and cadmium. Dr. Stern was a member of the National Research Council/National Academy of Sciences Committee on the Toxicology of Methylmercury (1999-2000) and a member of the recent USEPA Science Advisory Board panel for the National-Scale Mercury Risk Assessment for Coal- and Oil-Fired Electrical Generating Units (June-July 2011) as well as the USEPA Science Advisory Board Panel for Peer Review of the All-Ages Lead Model (Oct. 27-28, 2005). He has also served on numerous USEPA-IRIS review panels including Toxicological Review of Urea (Dec. 13, 2010, Panel Chair), Toxicological Review of Trichloroacetic Acid (Dec. 10, 2009, Panel Chair), Toxicological Review of 2-Hexanone (May 22, 2008, Panel Chair), Toxicological Review of Toluene (Feb. 5, 2004, Panel Chair). Other panels, committees and workshops include, ATSDR Toxicological Profile Review of Revised Minimal Risk Levels (MRLs) for 1,4-Dioxane (March-April, 2010), ATSDR Toxicological Profile Review of Revised Inhalation MRL for 1,4-dioxane (Sept. 2011), USEPA Panel for the Review of Draft Exposure Factors Handbook (March 3-4, 2010), USEPA Workshop on Cardiovascular Toxicity of Methylmercury (Jan. 12-13, 2010), USEPA Panel for Review of —Draft Child-Specific Exposure Factors Handbook (Sept. 19-20, 2007). Dr. Stern has authored numerous articles in peer-reviewed journals, and contributed a book chapter on Exposure Assessment for Neurotoxic Metals in —Human Developmental Neurotoxicology - D. Bellinger, ed. (Taylor & Francis, New York, 2006.), and the article on *Environmental Health Risk*

Assessment // in the *Encyclopedia of Quantitative Risk Assessment and Analysis*. John Wiley and Sons Ltd., 2008.

Appendix 2. Meeting Agenda

Workshop VIII Agenda

Agenda

Date: May 21 & 22, 2014

Location: Texas Commission on Environmental Quality, Austin, Texas

Purpose: To advance the recommendations of NAS (2009) and subsequent framework of ARA (2013) on problem formulation and dose-response analysis, through review of illustrative case studies for further development of methods

All times are Central Daylight Time.

Wednesday May 21st

Welcome (8:30 am)

- **Richard Hyde, P.E., Executive Director of the Texas Commission on Environmental Quality**
- Introduction and Opening Remarks (8:40 to 8:50)
 - **Members of the Advisory Committee and Science Panel**
- Keynote Talk: EPA's Risk Assessment Forum activity related to the Science and Decisions Report (8:50 to 9:35)
 - **Rita Schoeny, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency**

Morning Break (9:30 to 10:00)

Review of Case Study: Weight of Evidence Approach for Chemicals with Limited Toxicity Data (silanes and siloxanes) (10:00 to noon)

- **Tiffany Bredfeldt, Texas Commission on Environmental Quality**
- **Science Panel discussion**

Lunch (noon to 1:00)

Beyond Science and Decisions Dose Response Assessment Framework (1:00 to 1:30)

- **Lynne Haber, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment**

Dose-response assessment of a mixture of melamine and cyanuric acid in rats: practical challenges and outcome (1:30 to 2:15)

- **Gonçalo Gamboa da Costa, National Center for Toxicological Research**

Kids and Chemical Safety (2:15 to 3:00)

- **Patricia Nance, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment**

Afternoon Break (3:00 to 3:30)

Understanding Uncertainties and Confidence in Hazard Databases: An Example Using IRIS
(3:30 to 4:15)

- **Nancy Beck, American Chemistry Council**

Observer Comments (4:15 to 5:00)

Reception (dinner portion hors d'oeuvres, 6:30 to 9:00)

Thursday, May 22nd

Review of Case Study: Practical guidance on the development of a non-cancer hazard range for effective risk assessment and risk management of contaminated sites: A case study with trichloroethylene and other chemicals. (8:00 to 10:00)

- **Ed Pfau of Hull and Associates and Rod Thompson of Alliance for Site Closure**

Morning Break (10:00 to 10:30)

Practical Guidance ... (continued) (10:30 to noon)

- **Science Panel discussion**

Lunch (noon to 1:00)

Lessons learned from the U.S. Endocrine Disruptor Screening Programs (1:00 to 1:45)

- **Ellen Mihaich, *ER*²**

Case Study Proposal: Comparative risk assessment of mixtures in fish (1:45 to 2:30)

- **Michael Dourson, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment**
- **Coauthor: Moiz Mumtaz, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry**

Observer Comments and Closing remarks (2:30 to 3:00)

Adjourn

Appendix 3. List of Workshop Participants

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Beyond Science and Decisions: Workshop VI

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Beyond Science and Decisions: Workshop VI

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